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Effective Management Of School Facilities On Teaching And Learning Senior Secondary Schools In Sokoto North Local Government, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

School facilities have been seen as potential factors to quality education in terms of teaching and learning. This study examined the management of facilities and school performance. The specific objectives include: influence of management of classroom facilities on teaching and learning, management of co-curricular facilities on co-curricular activities and impact of management of discipline facilities on student discipline. A survey research design was used to gather detailed information from respondents. A total of three hundred and sixty eight (368) respondents drawn from administrators, teachers and students were selected as sample for the study with the use of random and purposive sampling techniques. The research instrument used to collect data for the study was questionnaire. Reliability of PFSPQ was established with the use of test-retest reliability with a value of 0.74 and validity was determined through face and content validity with a CVI value of 0.78. Three hundred and sixty eight (368) questionnaires were administered to respondents in the three (3) randomly selected secondary schools in Sokoto North Local government. However, three hundred and eighteen (318) questionnaires were returned. The major findings of this study are management of classroom facilities has influence on the management of teaching and learning, the management of co-curricular facilities has influence on co-curricular activities and management of discipline facilities has impact on students' discipline in secondary schools. Based on these findings, it is recommended that all stakeholders in education especially the government should improve on school facilities such that the pressure mounted by increase in students' enrolment on the physical facilities could be addressed to ensure effective teaching and learning. Administrators and teachers should ensure full participation of students in co-curricular activities both in the schools and among students of other schools to sow, cultivate and instill a sense of belonging among students of different ethnic backgrounds with different ways of life; and that they should also maintain proper educational standards and discipline among students in the schools hence school rules and regulations should be emphasized to protect school facilities.

Keywords: Facilities, co-curricular activities, discipline, classroom, students and teachers

INTRODUCTION

Facilities management is a crucial aspect of the overall management of a school. They play important roles in the attainment of the school's intended objectives. Education on the other hand forms the basis upon which economic, social and political development of any nation is founded. Investment in education can help to foster economic growth, enhance productivity, contribute to national and social development, and reduce social inequality (UNESCO, 2008). Facilities are everything used directly or indirectly for the benefit of education. Facilities could also be explained as the entire school plant such as blocks of classrooms, staffrooms, laboratories, workshops, libraries, laboratory equipment, consumables, audio-visual aids, electricity, water, chairs, tables, stationeries, playground, storage spaces and others which school has. It has always been realized that facilities are very important in the development and improvement of education (Philius and Wanjobi, 2011).

A school without facilities, either private or public, may not be able to achieve the stated goals and objectives of the system. When facilities are available and skillfully utilized, they influence learning and make it more meaningful. Facilities in education are very vital because they aid teaching and learning. Balogun (2002) noted that the importance of facilities cannot be overlooked. Facilities like modern laboratories, libraries and classrooms are to be put in place in all our schools. Adesola (2005) found out that the level of available resources is indeed a plus to the teachers and thereby shows the level of ingenuity and commitment of the teachers toward effective delivery of lessons. There is the need for renovation of old buildings, chairs, desks, cabinets and acquisition of modern classrooms as recommended by Alimi (2007). Akande (2005) identified facilities as a major factor contributing to academic performance in the schools system. These include classroom furniture, recreational equipment among others. Different studies conducted by Akinwumiju and Orimoloye (2007), showed that a positive relationship exists between availability of facilities and student academic performances. The effective management of school facilities is a critical factor influencing teaching and learning outcomes, particularly in senior secondary schools. In the context of Sokoto North Local Government, Sokoto State, Nigeria, the relevance of school facilities and infrastructure cannot be overstated. Research indicates that adequate school facilities significantly contribute to academic excellence by enhancing the teaching and learning process. For instance, a study highlights that instructional materials and infrastructure play a vital role in attracting and retaining qualified teachers, which ultimately helps in harnessing students' potential ("Relevance of School Facilities and Infrastructure Towards Implementing Education Policies", 2023). This assertion is supported by findings that emphasize the deep impact of physical facilities on the teaching-learning process, suggesting that well-maintained and adequately equipped schools foster better educational outcomes (Saeed et al., 2019).

Moreover, the maintenance and management of school facilities are essential for sustaining their effectiveness. 's research underscores the importance of regular assessments of school facilities to ensure they meet educational standards and support effective learning environments (Ahmad, 2021). This aligns with findings that advocate for systematic management practices to enhance the quality of educational infrastructure, thereby improving student performance (Pakpahan & Hidayati, 2021). In particular, the design and maintenance of school facilities are crucial, as poor infrastructure can adversely affect both student and teacher health, which in turn impacts the overall teaching and learning experience (Pakpahan & Hidayati, 2021).

In the Nigerian context, studies have shown that the state of school facilities varies significantly, with many schools facing challenges related to maintenance and management. For example, research conducted in Delta State revealed that inadequate facilities and poor maintenance practices hinder the effective management of educational resources (Asiyai, 2012). This highlights the necessity for school administrators to engage in proactive management strategies to ensure that facilities are not only available but also conducive to learning (Asiyai, 2012). Furthermore, the integration of technology in school facilities has been identified as a key factor in enhancing educational quality. The positive correlation between the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in teaching and learning processes has been well documented, indicating that schools that effectively utilize ICT resources tend to achieve better educational outcomes (Ayub et al., 2012; Goldhaber, 2021).

The effective management of school facilities is paramount for improving teaching and learning in senior secondary schools in Sokoto North Local Government. The interplay between adequate

infrastructure, maintenance practices, and the integration of technology creates a conducive environment for academic success. Continued research and investment in school facilities are essential to address existing challenges and enhance the quality of education in the region.

Statement of the Problems

The effective management of school facilities is a pressing issue in senior secondary schools within Sokoto North Local Government, Sokoto State, Nigeria. Several problems have been identified that hinder the optimal utilization of these facilities, ultimately affecting the teaching and learning processes.

Firstly, the inadequacy of school facilities is a significant concern. Research indicates that the availability and quality of educational facilities directly correlate with student performance and overall educational outcomes ("Relevance of School Facilities and Infrastructure Towards Implementing Education Policies", 2023; Sabit, 2019). In many schools within Sokoto North, there is a lack of essential facilities such as classrooms, libraries, and laboratories, which are crucial for fostering an effective learning environment. This inadequacy not only limits the resources available for teaching but also demotivates both teachers and students, leading to subpar academic performance (Dewi et al., 2023).

Secondly, poor maintenance and management of existing facilities exacerbate the situation. Effective management practices are essential for ensuring that school facilities are not only available but also functional and conducive to learning (Nuryani et al., 2021). However, many schools in Sokoto North suffer from inadequate maintenance routines, leading to dilapidated infrastructure that can pose health risks to students and staff (Pakpahan & Hidayati, 2021). The lack of systematic management strategies often results in the neglect of facilities, which further diminishes their effectiveness in supporting educational activities (Riswandi et al., 2023).

Additionally, financial constraints significantly impact the management of school facilities. Many schools struggle with insufficient funding, which limits their ability to upgrade or maintain facilities adequately (Parveen et al., 2021). This financial shortfall often leads to prioritizing immediate operational needs over long-term infrastructure improvements, creating a cycle of neglect that is difficult to break (Owoeye & Yara, 2011). Consequently, the lack of investment in school facilities can hinder the implementation of modern educational practices, including the integration of technology, which is increasingly vital for enhancing learning experiences ("Management of Educational Facilities and Infrastructure to Support Centre Model Learning for Kindergarten Teachers It Baitusshalihin Banda Aceh, Indonesia", 2023).

Moreover, the involvement of stakeholders in the planning and management of school facilities is often minimal. Effective facility management requires collaboration among school administrators, teachers, parents, and the community (Dewi et al., 2023). However, in Sokoto North, there is frequently a disconnect between school authorities and stakeholders, resulting in poorly informed decisions regarding facility needs and management strategies ("Relevance of School Facilities and Infrastructure Towards Implementing Education Policies", 2023). This lack of stakeholder engagement can lead to misalignment between the facilities provided and the actual needs of the students and teachers, further complicating the management of school resources.

The effective management of school facilities in senior secondary schools in Sokoto North Local Government is hindered by inadequate facilities, poor maintenance practices, financial constraints, and insufficient stakeholder involvement. Addressing these issues is crucial for enhancing the teaching and learning environment, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes for students.

Objectives Of The Study

This study pursues the following objectives:

1. To examine the influence of management of classroom facilities on teaching and learning in secondary schools.
2. To examine the influence of management of co-curricular facilities on co-curricular activities in secondary schools.

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁ There is no significance influence on teaching and learning in secondary schools. Management of co-curricular facilities does not have significant influence on the co-curricular activities in secondary schools.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The effective management of school facilities plays a crucial role in enhancing teaching and learning outcomes in senior secondary schools. A review of related literature reveals several key themes regarding the management of school facilities and their impact on educational processes, particularly in the context of Sokoto North Local Government, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

One of the primary themes in the literature is the importance of adequate planning and involvement of stakeholders in the management of school facilities. They emphasize that effective planning for educational facilities and infrastructure is essential for determining the needs of schools and facilitating the learning process (Dewi et al., 2023). This planning should involve various stakeholders, including school administrators, teachers, and the community, to ensure that the facilities meet the actual needs of the students and support effective learning environments ("Relevance of School Facilities and Infrastructure Towards Implementing Education Policies", 2023). The literature suggests that when stakeholders are engaged in the planning process, the resulting facilities are more likely to be utilized effectively, thereby enhancing educational outcomes.

Another critical aspect highlighted in the literature is the relationship between school infrastructure and student learning outcomes. Research indicates that the quality of school facilities significantly influences students' academic performance. For instance, points out that external factors, such as school infrastructure, play a vital role in shaping students' learning outcomes (Srijayanti, 2023). Similarly, asserts that the availability of appropriate facilities directly affects the quality of the learning process and, consequently, student achievement (Dewi, 2023). This underscores the necessity for schools in Sokoto North to prioritize the development and maintenance of adequate facilities to foster a conducive learning environment.

Moreover, the literature emphasizes the need for regular maintenance and management of school facilities. discusses the importance of systematic data collection regarding the condition of school facilities, which can inform maintenance and improvement efforts (Ahmad, 2021). Regular assessments and timely maintenance are crucial for ensuring that facilities remain functional and conducive to learning. This is particularly pertinent in Sokoto North, where many schools face challenges related to infrastructure deterioration due to inadequate maintenance practices (Mandacan, 2023).

Financial constraints also emerge as a significant barrier to effective facility management. The literature indicates that insufficient funding often limits schools' ability to maintain and upgrade facilities, which can negatively impact the quality of education (Attsaury, 2023). This financial challenge is compounded by the need for schools to prioritize immediate operational needs over long-term infrastructure improvements, creating a cycle of neglect that is difficult to overcome (Hasanah et al., 2023). Addressing these financial constraints is essential for enhancing the management of school facilities and improving educational outcomes in Sokoto North.

Finally, the literature highlights the implications of school facilities on teachers' pedagogical practices. The presence of adequate facilities is linked to improved teacher performance and satisfaction, which in turn positively impacts student learning (Pakpahan & Hidayati, 2021). For instance, research shows that well-equipped classrooms can enhance teachers' ability to deliver effective instruction and engage students in the learning process (Oluremi & Olubukola, 2012). Therefore, investing in school facilities not only benefits students but also supports teachers in their professional roles.

In conclusion, the effective management of school facilities in senior secondary schools in Sokoto North is influenced by various factors, including stakeholder involvement in planning, the quality of infrastructure, regular maintenance practices, financial constraints, and the impact on teachers' pedagogical effectiveness. Addressing these issues is vital for enhancing the teaching and learning environment and improving educational outcomes in the region.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

There are twenty (7) senior secondary schools in Sokoto North Local Government. The seven senior secondary schools have a population of 26,111 students with 7 Principal and 996 teachers. The sample for this study is three (3) selected secondary schools. The schools were selected because they offer double sift system due to inadequate facilities. A total of 368 respondents were randomly selected from the total population of 8,845 based on Krejcie and Morgan (1970). Six (9) school administrators (Principals and Vice Principal), fifteen (15) teachers five from each school and three hundred and

forty seven (347) students of the selected three Senior Secondary schools were sampled. Two sets of questionnaires were administered to teachers/administrators and students. The questionnaire was divided into six sections A, B, C, D, E and F with 40 question items for each group of the respondents. Section A contains items related to classroom facilities, section B deals with items on teaching and learning, section C has the items on co-curricular facilities, section D consists of items related to co-curricular activities, section E is for discipline facilities while F deals with students' discipline. All questions used dichotomous responses (Yes=1, No=2). To ensure validity of the research instruments; pilot testing of some copies of the questionnaires were done. The questionnaire was given to experts in the field of education to assess the instrument; this has helped to take care of the language clarity, the ability of the instrument to tap information from respondents, acceptability in terms of length and to provide ethical considerations for respondents. By so doing content validity index value was established as 0.78 which is above the 0.7 standard value for validity. Hence, the instrument was considered valid for use in the study. Test-retest reliability coefficient was used to establish reliability of the instrument to be used in the study, the value got was 0.74. This value indicated a good degree of reliability of the entire questionnaire, as supported by Kothari (2004) and Gray (2004). Hence, it is proved that the questionnaire is reliable and suitable for the study. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) and chi square statistical tool using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) based on Martin and Acuna (2002).

RESULTS

The analysis revealed that majority (83.3%) of the administrators, 61.5% of the teachers and 66.2% of the students agreed that the classrooms have adequate teachers' chairs and tables; all (100.0%) of the administrators and teachers and overwhelming majority (91.6%) of the students agreed that there are adequate furniture for example chairs and tables where students sit and write; all (100.0%) of the administrators and teachers and overwhelming majority (88.3%) of the students agreed that the school mend broken furniture; all (100.0%) of the administrators, 76.9% of the teachers and 80.3% of the students agreed that classrooms have enough dust bins and are regularly emptied; and all (100.0%) of the administrators and teachers and majority (75.3%) of the students agreed that classrooms have adequate chalkboards while majority of the administrators (83.3%), teachers (61.5%) and students (76.3%) disagreed that the classrooms have wall clocks; and 83.3% of the administrators, 69.2% of the teachers and 73.6% of the students are of the opinion that classrooms have displayed time tables. The analysis also revealed that all the administrators (100.0%), majority of the teachers (84.6%) and students (82.6%) agreed that there is lack of enough classrooms and these forces teachers to conduct lessons under trees even in rainy seasons; all the administrators (100.0%), 76.9% of the teachers and 83.6% of the students agreed that teachers complain about teaching load being more because of lack of teaching facilities; all the administrators (100.0%), 76.9% of the teachers and 87.0% of the students are of the opinion that students participate in class activities; all the administrator (100.0%), 69.2% of the teachers and 82.3% of the students agreed that students do not concentrate because of many students in the class while 88.3% of the administrators and 72.6% of the students agreed that students have enough seats to do their exercises but 53.8% of the teachers disagreed. In order to ascertain the influence of management of classroom facilities on teaching and learning in secondary schools, the above results were analysed using chi-square statistical tool.

Table 1: Chi-square test for the influence of management of classroom facilities on teaching and learning Value

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	25.110	13	.008
Likelihood Ratio	23.150	13	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	21.632	13	.001
N of Valid Cases	318		

Results presented in table 1 showed the value for the influence of management of classroom facilities on teaching and learning in secondary schools in Sokoto North Local Government, as 25.110 (P_value

= 0.008 < 0.05), indicating a statistically significant influence of management of classroom facilities on teaching and learning. Therefore, management of classroom facilities has significant influence on teaching and learning in those secondary schools in Sokoto North metropolis, Nigeria. The analysis further revealed that majority of the administrators (66.7%) and the teachers (69.2%) agreed that there is a football pitch in the school but students (50.8%) disagreed; half of the administrators (50.0%), 84.9% of the teachers and 64.5% of the students disagreed that the school hall is too small or not big enough; 83.3% of the administrators, 76.9% of the teachers and 51.8% of the students are of opinion that there is a volleyball court in their school; 88.3% of the administrators, 76.9% of the teachers and 51.2% of the students agreed that the school has a netball court; 66.7% of the administrators, 61.5% of the teachers agreed that the school has musical instruments but 59.2% of the students did not agree; 50.0% of the administrators, 61.5% of the teachers and 58.2% of the students agreed that their school has sport equipment like balls. 66.7% of the administrators, 61.5% of the teachers and 58.2% of the students said that their school does not have a swimming pool. Majority of the administrators (83.3%), the teachers (84.6%) and the students (87.6%) agreed that their school participates in football competition every year ; all the administrators (100.0%), 84.9% of the teachers and 64.5% of the students agreed that their school participates in both inter-school and intra-school debate competition; 66.7% of the administrators and 69.2% of the teachers are of opinion that their school offers dance and drama for students but 50.2% of the students disagreed; 50.0% of the administrators and 61.5% of the teachers agreed that their school organizes musical programmes for students but 51.2% of the students were not in agreement; 50.0% of the administrators, 53.8% of the teachers and 61.5% of the students said their school does not always organize graduation ceremony for outgoing students; 53.8% of the teachers and the students disagreed that their school participates in quiz competition but 66.7% of the administrators agreed. 83.3% of the administrators, 76.9% of the teachers and 68.2% of the students said that there are no clay modeling competition amongst students in their schools.

In order to ascertain the influence of management of co-curricular facilities on co-curricular activities in secondary schools, the above results were analysed using chi-square statistical tool.

Table 2: Chi-square test for hypothesis one Value

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.129	13	.000
Likelihood Ratio	14.799	13	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	17.150	13	.000
N of Valid Cases	318		

Results presented in table 2 showed that value for the influence of the management of co-curricular facilities on co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Sokoto North metropolis, Nigeria as 16.129 (P_value = 0.000 < 0.05) indicating that the result is statistically significant. Therefore, management of co-curricular facilities has an influence on co-curricular activities in secondary schools in Sokoto North metropolis, Nigeria. The analysis further revealed that all the administrators (100.0%), the teachers (76.9%) and the students (88.6%) agreed that schools have guideline book for discipline. All the administrators (100.0%), 76.9% of the teachers and 85.3% of the students agreed that there are counseling offices in their schools. Majority of the administrators (66.7%), overwhelming majority of the teachers and the students (92.3%) agreed that there are canes in their schools. Majority of the administrators (66.7%), the teachers (76.9%) and the students (68.6%) agreed that there is availability of mosques and churches in their schools for moral guidance. Also, all the administrators (100.0%), majority of the teachers (84.6%) and the students (86.6%) agreed that there are availability of instruments to discipline students e.g. cutlass and brooms for students to work with. Majority of the administrators (66.7%), the teachers (69.2%) and the students (72.2%) agreed that there are regular updating of school’s rules and regulations to suit the present situation. Similarly, majority of the administrators (50.0%), the teachers (53.8%) and the students (57.2%) agreed that their schools have security guards to watch students discipline.

DISCUSSION

The study found that there were adequate furniture for example chairs and tables where students sit and write. The broken furniture and chalkboards are always repaired. The classrooms have enough dust bins which are always emptied, chalkboards, chalkboards dusters, however no wall clocks and no displayed time tables. This means that there is a good management of school facilities in those secondary schools despite not being provided with adequate classroom facilities. Hence, the administrators and teachers try to manage the few classroom facilities in these schools. There were football pitches in those selected schools, their schools' halls were not big enough, there were volleyball and netball courts, their schools have musical instruments, their schools have sport equipments like balls but their schools did not have swimming pools.

The study finding also showed that schools have guideline book for discipline. There were counseling offices in these schools. There were canes, availability of mosques and churches in their schools for moral guidance. Also, there was availability of instruments to discipline students e.g. cutlass and brooms for them to work with. There was regular updating of school's rules and regulations to suit the present situation. Similarly, their schools had security guards to watch students so that they will be disciplined. The study similarly found that schools had guide lines book for discipline. The study also concluded that schools used to emphasize on students keeping to the school's rules and regulations. The schools were regularly updating their school rules and regulation to suit their present situation. There was regular guidance and counseling for all students. Schools always encouraged their students to be role models. Schools used to dismiss any student for misconduct. There are appropriate punishments for misbehavior by any student in the school but the number of students is too high for the school counselors. It was further found that schools used to emphasize on their rules and regulations to students and there are regular guidance and counseling for all students but the number of students is too many for school counselors to relate with. The schools also encourage students to be role models. There are regular updating of school's rules and regulations to suit the present situation, appropriate punishments for any misbehavior by any student and the school dismisses any student for misconduct. The findings are in agreement with Gold (2011) who concluded that heating and air conditioning systems appeared to be very important, along with special instructional facilities (science laboratories or equipment) and color and interior painting, in contributing to student achievement. It was found out that the quality of air inside public school facilities used to significantly affect students' ability to concentrate. Evidence proved that youth, especially those under ten years of age, are more vulnerable than adults to the types of contaminants (asbestos, radon, and formaldehyde) found in some school facilities (Amin, 2005).

Lowe (2009) noted that teachers pointed out that the availability and quality of classroom equipment and furnishings, as well as ambient features such as climate control and acoustics were the most important environmental factors to achieve proper teaching and learning. In particular, the teachers therefore emphasized that the ability to control classroom temperature is crucial to the effective performance of both students and teachers. This finding of the study is in line with Mugenda (2003) who concluded that high school athletes showed positive effects on extra-curricular involvement on academic achievement, Sarantakos (1997) observed that the participation in extra-curricular activities helped students in their academic performance. Booth (2008) also reported that participation of students in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities especially in sports, field visit and social service helped them to perform well academically. Aikman and Halter (2005) also noted that adolescents that participated in co-curricular activities reported higher grades, more positive attitudes towards school and higher academic aspirations. Darling (2000) found that there is a strong relationship between sports participation and academic achievement. Seber and Wilder (1997) observed that students who actively participate in one of the sports activities do well in their studies and that majority of students who engaged in co-curricular activities tend to attend school regularly. The findings in this study confirmed the conclusion from Okumbe (2001) who observed that based upon a literature review and an analysis of best practices; it seems almost self-evident that students engagement in co-curricular activities influences their academic achievement. The influence of learners' participation in school co-curricular activities has a positive impact on student academic performance.

CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that management of classroom facilities has significant influence on teaching and learning in these secondary schools. The study therefore found out that teachers try their best to manage the few classroom facilities to have effective teaching and learning. Finding shows that teachers' effort is yielding positive results as there is an influence of management of classroom facilities on teaching and learning. It was further concluded that management of co-curricular facilities has an influence on co-curricular activities in secondary schools. Finally, it was concluded that discipline facilities have an impact on the management of students' discipline in secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study on the management of facilities and school performance in secondary schools in Sokoto North Local Government, it is recommended that:

(i) All stakeholders in education especially the government should improve on classroom facilities such that the pressure mounted by increase in students' enrolment on the facilities could be addressed to ensure effective teaching and learning.

(ii) Administrators and teachers should ensure full participation of students in co-curricular activities both in the schools and among students of other schools to sow, cultivate and instill a sense of belonging or "esprit de corps" among students of different ethnic backgrounds and different ways of life.

(iii) Administrators and teachers should maintain educational standards and discipline among students in the schools to show that school rules and regulations are emphasized to protect school facilities.

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